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SECOND REPORT

DISCOVERY PROJECTS

**Sloane Lab:
Looking Back to Build
Future Shared Collections**

JUNE 2023

**University College London | The British Museum
Natural History Museum**

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
Abstract	4
Aims and Objectives	5
Partnership Structure	6
Staffing Structure	9
Overall Programme	11
Events and Consultations	12
Research Approach	19
Research Results	23
Project Outputs.....	28
Cross Project Collaboration	29
Sustainability and Infrastructure	30
Interim Recommendations	31
Contacts.....	32
Annex	33

Authors

Julianne Nyhan (UCL), Andreas Vlachidis (UCL), Andrew Flinn (UCL), Nina Pearlman (UCL), Mark Carine (Natural History Museum), Jeremy Hill (The British Museum)

Executive Summary

How can museums, libraries, archives and galleries (GLAMs) use digital technology to link their collections together in ways that make it easier for different people, both specialists and interested publics, to find the information they want? How can digital technology help us tell new stories about what can be rediscovered and reimagined by linking collections? How can we make specialist users and members of the public more aware of the contested nature and histories of museum collections? What is the role of digital tools in foregrounding overlooked or hidden processes, like imperialism, colonialism, transatlantic slavery, loss and destruction, that have shaped the national collection? Who gets to contribute to, and shape, research on how memory institutions can reach across their institutional boundaries, subject-specialities and even countries so as to better engage their varied audiences? And how can heritage institutions select the most useful technologies from the many that are available for digitising, releasing and interlinking their collections? These are the questions to which the Sloane Lab: Looking back to build future shared collections is responding.

Taking the collections assembled by Sir Hans Sloane as an exemplary case study that is expected to be transferable to the wider collections as data context, the project is uniting surviving Sloane objects, records and knowledge across the Natural History Museum (NHM), British Museum (BM) and British Library (BL) from the original catalogues, also furthering understandings of the extent and provenance of Sloane's original 1753 collection, the founding national collection of the BM. Bringing Sloane's historical catalogues and present-day cataloguing systems together, linking to other digital collections, and learning how to better support different ways to search and accommodate any "curious or interested person", the project is also addressing what is missing and contested. By working directly with local, regional, national and international heritage partners to devise trans-institutional methodologies for the integration of other collections with the Sloane Lab we hope to advance collections as data in the context of the holdings of UK galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM). Our work will be crystallised in the Sloane Lab, where the reunified and extended digital collection will be made searchable and amenable to further analysis and interpretation using a range of digital tools and processes.

Our project, Sloane Lab: Looking back to build future shared collections has made excellent progress since its initiation on 1 October 2022. Turning firstly to summarise the essential project governance data and set-up processes that have been completed: as of March 2023, a full cohort of project staff has been appointed, and all necessary Human Resources and management requirements and processes pertaining to their employment completed. UCL's Ethics Review Board has reviewed the project and granted its proposed plan of work the necessary approval; likewise, all data protection and data assurance processes have been set up and approved by the relevant UCL committee.

Collaboration agreements have been agreed between all partners. Data has been licensed to the Sloane Lab by the British Museum and the Natural History Museum under different licenses, namely to the extent the Materials are provided by, or attributable to, NHM and contain Metadata, such Metadata is licensed under Creative Commons CC Zero; to the extent the Materials are provided by, or attributable to, NHM and do not contain Metadata, such Materials are licensed under Creative Commons Attribution

CC BY, and shall be credited as © copyright of The Trustees of the Natural History Museum, London (as applicable); and (c) to the extent Materials are provided by, or attributable to, the British Museum (whether or not containing Metadata), such Materials are licensed under Creative Commons Attribution Share-Alike CC-BY-SA 4.0 and shall be credited as © copyright of The Trustees of the British Museum.

Sloane Lab is working to accommodate these different licenses in the following way: Different aggregations will have different namespaces; within aggregations, we will be using CIDOC-CRM to assign the various data rights at the level of individual record; visitors will be presented with a disclaimer about the varying dataset collection rights before getting into the Sloane Lab. Our model for this approach has been Wikidata enhanced with the fine-grained annotation of rights that CIDOC-CRM supports.

The research of the project is being pursued across three interconnected streams: the technical team, the participatory team, and the collections team.

As of March 2023, the technical team has completed the setup and deployment of the Sloane Lab technical infrastructure, including the set up and deployment of servers, portals, and schedules. The technical work package has moved into the core development phase where progress is continuous and incremental across all areas of data modelling, mobilisation, enrichment, and aggregation. Moreover, a coordinated effort between the technical and participatory work packages (WPs) has been established to promote co-design of preferable public-facing services and functionality of the Sloane Lab. Following the set-up of the technology stack and server infrastructure and the successful development of the alpha version of the knowledge base which aggregated the first set of historical catalogues (i.e., *Miscellanea*), the WP has progressed into further developments as described below in four distinct pathways. The key strategic priority is the satisfactory progress across the range of the development pathways with the aim to commence a full data-driven research process in early autumn 2023.

The community-focussed participatory work package team has continued in its work to engage diverse communities with the design of the Sloane Lab, seeking to involve our experts (academic, heritage professional and those from non-hegemonic communities) in the on-going process of designing the emergent Lab by exploring with them what questions (and crucially what type of questions) they might wish to ask of a digital national collection and to what extent the Lab can be developed and modified to support the widest possible engagement with collections and collections data and to answer the questions that diverse audiences might have. This participatory design process is a complex, iterative, and innovative one involving a reflective and circular design, moving from participatory engagements into discussions with the technical design and collections teams about the implications for the technical elaboration of the Sloane Lab infrastructure and information modelling and then back again to participatory groups. Building upon the detailed preparation and consultation with the Collections and Technical work packages in 2022, which led to the development of an agreed participatory plan for a range of co-creation activities with specialist, grassroot organisations, and non-hegemonic communities and the organisation of a pilot exercise of participatory activities with Sloane Lab Team members, this participatory team's programme of activities commenced in the last quarter of 2022. Amongst the events so far organised and completed are:

- 'Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab,' event held as part of NHM Explorers Family Festival (specifically an event focussed on those interested in African Caribbean family histories) with approximately 20 participants.

- ‘The Sloane Lab data challenge: engaging with and aggregating our challenging pasts,’ participatory workshop held as part of the 16th International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research and involving a diverse range of experts in data modelling, metadata, and semantics with 19 participants.
- ‘Connecting Jamaican plants across Sloane collections,’ participatory workshop involving those with significant interest and expertise in botanical specimens and Sloane’s collections, with 10 participants.

The findings from these workshops and focus groups are now being reviewed and shared with technical and collections’ teams to inform the development of the Lab and the type of questioning it can support. This work is being reflected in the on-going further cyclical planning of participatory events with seed heritage enthusiasts, gardeners and community groups, partner organisations in Northern Ireland (in collaborations with the Sloane Lab’s touring exhibition team) and African Caribbean community heritage groups in London. In addition, the participatory work package team has designed and produced a survey and expression of interest form which thus far has resulted in about 100 responses from academic and non-academic experts giving rich detail on their current experience and challenges in searching for and using relevant collections data as well as interest in participating in further co-design participatory Sloane Lab activities. The flagship of the participatory strand comprises ten Community Fellows who are appointed to undertake a creative, research led or practice-based project on the digital national collection using the Sloane Lab. Appointed through an open call, in light of the history of the Sloane Collection, applications are particularly welcomed from people of the Global Majority, disabled people, LGBTQI+ people, and women. Progress here too is notable, with three Community Fellows scheduled to begin work in April 2023, and the second Sloane Lab call to close on 15th May 2023

The Collections team comprises the Natural History Museum and the British Museum (with significant collaboration from the technical and participatory teams). The deliverables of the collections team include aspects of data mobilisation and the touring exhibition. The work of the collections team (BM and NHM) will advance both the project’s capacity to support data-driven collections as data research and exemplify the new kinds of knowledge that can be gained from this work.

The Collections team’s work on the Sloane Lab Touring Exhibition has significantly progressed. The Project Curator (Hughes) has led the work to develop the exhibition concept and the provisional title ‘For the Curious and the Interested’ was selected for the exhibition (this title draws on Sloane’s original intended audience for this collection when it came to the BM in 1753). The exhibition concept, and selection of objects, has been developed to encourage museum partners to explore themes around global collecting practices in the 17th and 18th centuries. The physical exhibition will ultimately aim to demonstrate the types of stories and connections that it will be possible to make via the Sloane Lab digital portal.

The data mobilisation that is another key deliverable of the Collections team’s work is progressing well. The Collections team is working closely with the technical team to carry out data review, catalogue data cleaning and enhancement, and to create a single data set of natural history specimens for data mobilisation. In the coming months, in addition to supervising community fellowships, the Collections team will also lead co-authored publications on *Historia Platarum* data mobilisation and cataloguing of the botanical collections (of course, co-authored papers will be written up by all three interconnected teams). This Collections team will also contribute to the planned trans-institutional case study, which will not only create new knowledge about the Sloane collection but act as a test bed for the Sloane Lab.

Abstract

The founding collection of the British Museum is a rich area to explore how we can reconnect dispersed heritage connections using state of the art technologies. This is because the British Museum's original 1753 founding collection of Sir Hans Sloane is now split across three different institutions (the British Museum (BM), Natural History Museum (NHM) and the British Library (BL)) and the digital information that describes this founding collection sits in the different institutions in a range of different systems that are not currently set up to talk to one another. By focusing on catalogue records, and the vast, remaining collections of Sir Hans Sloane, the Sloane Lab project is researching how we can work with interested communities and heritage organisations to link the present with the past so as to allow the currently broken links between Sloane's collections and catalogues to be re-established across the NHM, BL, BM (plus others that have relevant material).

The main outcome of our project will be a freely available, online digital lab (the Sloane Lab) that will offer researchers, curators and the interested public new opportunities to search, explore, and critically and creatively use and reuse digital cultural heritage.

Aims and Objectives

The aims and objectives that the Sloane Lab will deliver include:

- To devise automated and augmented ways that will be relevant to bringing together other collections in museums, galleries, libraries, and archives, of mending the broken links between the past and present of the UK's founding collection in the catalogues of the British Museum, Natural History Museum, and the British Library. For this, we will use the collection of Sir Hans Sloane (1660-1753) as a microcosm through which to explore the technical, infrastructural, conceptual, historical, and social challenges faced in bringing together digital cultural heritage collections so as to help audiences use, learn and benefit from them.
- To deliver the public-facing, open access Sloane Lab of content, tools, and applications, opening new ways for national digital collections to be researched, explored, interlinked, and creatively engaged with.
- To facilitate richer, more critical understandings of the origins and development of museum collections by devising computational and conceptual approaches to detecting and exposing often-hidden processes like colonialism, empire and slavery that have shaped collections and their classifications. Sloane's collection was created through the economic, political, and cultural processes of Britain's increasing global entanglements of the 17/18th century, to which the infrastructure for a 21st-century national collection must respond.
- To evaluate the role of AI, Digital Humanities, Data Science, and historical collection records in the infrastructure of the future national collection, disseminating our findings globally as open source and reusable demonstrators and best practice documentation.
- To engage in ongoing, participatory research with diverse audiences, project partners, and the wider heritage sector to elaborate a digital cultural heritage participatory research paradigm and methodology that accommodates a plurality of perspectives and voices and does not limit the publics to interacting with the national collection as curators, librarians, archivists, computer scientists and others have modelled it in existing platforms.
- To work with Heritage Institutions to identify factors like resources or investments that constrain an organisation's ability to contribute to national collection infrastructures and content and deliver policy recommendations for future digital heritage capacity and infrastructure investment.

Partnership Structure

Collaborators

The Sloane Lab is led by University College London (UCL) which oversees the research and technical trajectory and alignment (including ethical oversight and data protection) of the project as a whole, along with administrative and budgetary management and reporting on the project to AHRC and the TaNC Directorate. Further particulars of UCL's contributions to every work package of this project are given below. Project collaborators are the British Museum (BM) and Natural History Museum (NHM), where Co-Investigators Jeremy Hill (BM) and Mark Carine (NHM) oversee the execution of their respective institutions' deliverables for the project and supervise the Sloane Lab-funded project staff hired by their institutions. The NHM team work closely with the technical team to carry out data review, catalogue data cleaning and enhancement, and create a single data set of natural history specimens for data mobilisation. In terms of engagement activities, the NHM team will supervise some of the community fellowships. They will also lead publications on the mobilisation of data held in Sloane's copy of *Historia Plantarum* and cataloguing of Sloane's botanical collections. The team members in BM research topics to inform the technical team and work collaboratively on a trans-institutional case study. They will lead the research and preparation for the touring exhibition with a number of venues, including the Down County Museum. There will also be permanent display changes in BM. The BM team will also supervise some of the community fellows and, where fellows are amenable to the idea, it is hoped that fellows may also present their work at outreach events.

Project Partners

British Library

- To advise, including review of and input into project documentation, quarterly meetings, and active engagement/facilitation with Library colleagues and others outside the project.
- General curatorial and project support from teams within Western Heritage Collections responsible for managing Sloane collections.
- Provision of existing manuscript catalogue data from the Explore Archives and Manuscripts catalogue.
- Provision of catalogue records for printed books held by the British Library, derived and enhanced from the Sloane Printed Books catalogue, and supplied as MARC XML.

<p>Community Archives & Heritage Group</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share experiences and to explore how the different solutions developed by the project could address similar challenges and inform the future strategy and work of CAHG. • To encourage members of Community Archives to actively engage in the project's participatory research sessions and attend meetings where the learning from the research will be shared. • Advise on the project's dissemination activities aimed at Community Archives and potentially co-hosting a community-focused conference or workshop. • Advertise the Fellowships over CAHG networks and potentially give high-level feedback on Fellowship applications that fall in their remit.
<p>Collecting the West (Australian Research Council funded project)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Committed to meeting with the Sloane Lab team for at least one 2-3 hour meeting a year for three years for the purpose of knowledge exchange and with the potential to develop more connections with the Sloane Lab team and their partners in Australia. Additionally, a two and half day event in Deakin University, Melbourne. November 22nd to November 24th which will be jointly organised by the Sloane Lab and the <i>Collecting the West</i> project. The aim of the meeting is to bring together key Australian researchers and projects in collections histories and digital collections to share and discuss the state of the art of this research.
<p>Down County Museum (N. Ireland)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Host a travelling exhibition of key artefacts relating to Hans Sloane to help local people re-engage with the diverse aspects of Hans Sloane's legacy. It will be used as a touchstone to draw attention to the Sloane Lab project. • The Museum will use the Lab as a way to encourage its existing and new audiences to explore various themes relating to the lifetime and context of Sloane that are relevant to our lives today, including natural themes such as

	<p>biodiversity, and cultural themes such as the legacy of colonialism and the slave trade.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A loan exhibition on Hans Sloane will enable the museum to explore all aspects of museology, using both the digital Sloane Lab and its own collections to stimulate interest, debate, and audience participation.
<p>University of Oxford, Department of Plant Sciences</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge exchange on sharing digital collections, using digital tools to support the digitisation of collections information, and learning how better support different people to use the digital collections. • To explore how the different solutions developed by the project could address similar challenges and inform future work and strategy. • Contribution of staff time and potential for integration with other initiatives.
<p>University of Oxford, Gardens, Libraries and Museums</p>	
<p>Royal Botanic Garden Edinburgh</p>	
<p>National Museum of Scotland</p>	
<p>Historic Environment Scotland</p>	
<p>National Galleries of Scotland</p>	
<p>National Library of Scotland</p>	

Staffing Structure

Professor Julianne Nyhan, Principal Investigator (Professor of Digital Humanities, UCL and Professor of Humanities Data Science and Methodology, TU Darmstadt), is the principal investigator and intellectual lead of the project. Nyhan has overall responsibility for the research, technical and participatory direction of the project and for the line management of UCL-based PDRA's. Nyhan maintains a bird's eye view of the project, its progress and direction overall, tracking research execution and trajectory, including identifying required alignments and readjustments in work package outputs and looking ahead to ensure the preparations for each sequential stage of the project are in place in good time. Nyhan and all Co-Investigators also contribute to research output dissemination and delivery, including presenting the project at high-profile international events.

Dr Andrew Flinn, Deputy Principal Investigator and Co-Investigator (Reader in Archival Studies and Oral History, UCL). As co-investigator he supervises the work of the Participatory Consultant (Alda Terracciano) and co-leads the project's participatory strategy, implementation, and evaluation with Dr Nina Pearlman, working closely with Nyhan. Dr Flinn also opens pathways to community archives and heritage groups.

Dr Andreas Vlachidis, Co-Investigator (Assistant Professor in Information Science, UCL), is the technical lead of the project. He supervises the PDRA's implementation of technical architecture and leads the research of the methods for integrating the dispersed Sloane collection under a unified Knowledge Base. He also contributes to the work of the participatory design, liaising with the relevant team member in an iterative process that seeks to incorporate input into the design and development of the knowledge base and other connected dissemination of data retrieval and visualisation.

Dr Nina Pearlman, Co-Investigator (Head of UCL Art Collections, UCL), supervises the work of the Participatory PDRA (Marco Humbel) and co-leads the project's participatory strategy, implementation, and evaluation with Dr Andrew Flinn, working closely with Nyhan. Dr Pearlman also opens pathways to dispersed and living collections.

Dr Mark Carine, Co-Investigator (Principal Curator in Charge, Algae, Fungi, and Plants Division, Natural History Museum), is a herbarium curator responsible for Sloane's botanical collections. He supervises the NHM PDRA (Dr Victoria Pickering) and oversees the mobilisation of the NHM data with Sloane's taxonomic index to the herbarium as well as case study research.

Dr Jeremy Hill, Co-Investigator (Head of Research, The Directorate, The British Museum), supervises the BM Project Curator (Dr Alicia Hughes), the Exhibition Programme Manager (hired in year 2) and BM Consultant (Dr Kim Sloane), is responsible for coordinating the overall strategy and implementation of the BM touring exhibition and for communications regarding data exchange between the British Museum, UCL, Natural History Museum, British Library and other partners as relevant.

Dr Sushma Jansari, Co-Investigator (Tabo Foundation Curator: South Asia, The British Museum), will be assisted by the BM PDRA (Dr Alicia Hughes) and will lead changes to the BM permanent displays.

Dr Daniele Metilli, Research Fellow in Advanced Data Architectures for Digital Humanities (UCL), is responsible for the Sloane Lab metadata mapping, semantic data modelling, knowledge base design and development, including ontologies, linked data, and graph databases.

Dr Foteini Valeonti, Research Fellow in Systems Development and Research (UCL), is responsible for executing computational components and interfaces, enabling programmatic access to digital collections, data aggregation and federation and front-end (application) development.

Dr Jawad Sadek, Senior Research Fellow in Artificial Intelligence and Natural Language Processing (UCL), undertakes research on NLP and AI to implement solutions for information extraction, automatic handwritten text recognition and semantic enrichment of museum data and cultural heritage collections.

Marco Humbel, Research Fellow in Participatory Research and Collections as Data (UCL), is responsible for contributing to participatory research and design; for facilitating a series of participatory events with heritage organisations, and planning community fellowships.

Dr Victoria Pickering, Research Fellow (Natural History Museum), is responsible for mobilising Sloane's taxonomic index to the NHM's Sloane herbarium; executing machine actionable versions of Sloane catalogues, case study research, as well as supporting the community fellows.

Dr Alicia Hughes, Project Curator (The British Museum), is engaged in mobilising data on Sir Hans Sloane's collections held at the British Museum, as well as researching case studies on Sloane's collections and supporting the community fellows.

Dr Kim Sloan, Historical Consultant (The British Museum), is an acknowledged expert on Sloane and PI on previous AHRC and Leverhulme-funded projects on Sloane's collection.

Dr Alda Terracciano, Community Consultant (UCL), provides consultancy on the elaboration of participatory methodologies and instruments for working with diverse communities and for the planning and delivery of engagement events.

Rosalyn Tyler, Exhibition Programme Manager (The British Museum) planning the development and delivery of the touring exhibition programme.

Ciara Adeniyi-Jones, Project Administrator (UCL), serves as the first point of contact for all stakeholders, and coordinates all participatory events and communication channels. She also assists with reporting to AHRC and documentation of findings of participatory events.

Overall Programme

Year	2021			2022												2023												2024									Post-project period			Lead*:	
Calendar Month	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12		
Activities /Deliverables	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	Post-project period				
WP 1 - Participatory and Engagement activities																																									
1.1	Planning and preparation																																							Part	
1.2	Workshops x 10: Query Service & KB																																							Part	
1.3	One-to-one sessions & testing/demo sessions: data modelling																																							Part	
1.4	Workshop x 2 & online tasks: Data Atlas																																							Part	
1.5	Workshop x 4: API & Web Application (Data discovery)																																							Part	
1.6	Community Fellowships (CF): Sloane Lab data model																																							Part	
1.7	Community Fellowships (CF): API & Web Applications																																							Part	
1.8	Community Fellowships (CF): Final iteration																																							All	
WP 2 - Technological Actions																																									
2.1	Datasets Review and Acquisition																																							Tech	
2.2	Setup and Install Technology Stack																																							Tech	
2.3	Design and Refine Data Model																																							Tech	
2.4	Prepare and Map Data																																							Tech	
2.5	Enrich and Ingest Data																																							Tech	
2.6	Deploy Sloane Lab																																							Tech	
2.7	Disseminate SL Framework																																							Tech	
2.8	Develop Tools and Web Services																																							Tech	
2.9	Publish Linked Data																																							Tech	
2.10	Documentation																																							Tech	
WP 3 Collections Work Package																																									
3.1	NHM data review																																							CT	
3.2	NHM Catalogue data cleaning and enhancement																																							CT	
3.3	Vegetable Substances collection (data set mobilisation)																																							CT	
3.4	Creation of a single data set of Nat Hist specimens in NHM																																							CT	
3.5	Ray Historia Plantarum I & II - data mobilisation																																							CT	
3.6	Ray Historia Plantarum III (appendices) - data mobilisation																																							CT	
3.9	BM Research topics to inform Technical Team																																							CT	
3.10	BM Research & Preparation for Exhibition with Downpatrick Museum																																							CT	
3.11	Exhibition opens in Downpatrick																																							CT	
3.12	Preparation to tour exhibition to other venues																																							CT	
3.13	Research & Preparation for BM display changes																																							CT	
3.14	BM Display changes open to public																																							CT	
3.15	Trans-institutional case study																																							All	
WP4 Reporting and dissemination																																									
4.1	AHRC/TaNC Written Reports																																							All	
4.2	Report during meetings																																							All	
4.3	Conference and Publications																																							All	

*Lead: sub-team that lead activities and deliverables

Part = Participatory Team; Tech = Technical Team; CT = Collections Team (BM & NHM)

Alpha Release

Beta Release

Final Release

Annual Project Review

Annual Project Review

Events and Consultations

Consultations

Dates	Consultations	No. of attendees / Respondents
14 Oct 2021	Meeting with the Royal Society (RS) to introduce the Sloane Lab and catch up with RS on the development of their digitisation programme. RS offered to do a survey of the Sloane material and was interested in joining the Advisory Board for the wider consultation and contribute to the project.	Attendees include RS Head of Library and Information Services, Digital Resources Manager, Sloane Lab (SL) PI and Historical Consultant of Sloane Lab.
16 Dec 2021	A follow-up meeting with the Royal Society to discuss Sloane data provided by RS.	Attendees include the Head of Library and Information Services, Digital Resources Manager, and Technical Lead of SL
14 Jan 2022	Meeting with Down County Museum Curator and CEO/Founder of Sir Hans Sloane Centre to discuss the scope of the partnership and the role of Down County Museum in the touring exhibition.	Attendees include Down County Museum Curator and CEO/Founder of Sir Hans Sloane Centre, BM Head of National Programmes, and SL team members
19 Jan 2022	Initial Meeting with Project Partners and Advisory Board The purpose of the meeting was to introduce Sloane Lab to the partner organisations and Advisory Board and to invite support from them. The team explained the background of the TaNC Programme, as well as the research approach of the project.	Total attendance 36, including 26 from partner organisations and the Sloane Lab advisory Board members who located internationally.
16 Feb 2022	Meeting with BM & NHM colleagues to introduce the Sloane Lab participatory and engagement plan and consultations.	Attendees include NHM UX Manager, BM Community Engagement Consultant, BM Head of National Programmes, and SL participatory team.

24 Mar 2022	Meeting with British Library to discuss how BL could engage with the Sloane Lab project, also the areas of involvement and consultations. The various BL curator also gave overviews on the Sloane materials housing in BL, and some technical practicalities.	Total attendance 10, including Head of Western Heritage Collections and Curators.
20 Apr 2022	Meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting The West (CTW). Following a brief overview of both the technical and participatory methods of SL, the group discussed the possible knowledge exchange areas; including overlaps of the two projects on how to handle and aggregate data and shared experience on community engagement	Total attendance 11, including 3 from the CTW.
4 May 2022	Year 1 Advisory Board meeting Apart from reporting on Work Packages, the project team sought the expertise and experience of the Advisory board in connection with a number of questions, such as best practices in the integration of dispersed data sets and including the voices of small heritage organisations and non-hegemonic communities.	Total attendance 26, including 12 from the SL Advisory Board.
5 – 6 May 2022	Jeremy Hill (Co-I) and BM Head of National Programmes N. Ireland visit. He met with Down County Museum CEO and other staff for Sloane Lab travel exhibition planning.	Down County Museum and Sir Hans Sloane Centre staff members
20 May 2022	Meeting with UCL Copyright Officer (Referred by Advisory Board member) for consultation on CC Licence and IP of reusing Sloane Lab materials.	Attendance: UCL Copyright Officer, PI and Project Administrator
23 Oct 2022	Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab. A half day digital jam workshop designed by Alda Terracciano and produced in collaboration with Marco Humbel as part of the NHM Explorers Family Festival.	Target group: British-Caribbean people interested in plants. Number of participants: 20

02 Nov 2022	<p>Meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting the West (CTW).</p> <p>Initial exploratory consultation with Collecting the West team. Members of each Sloane Lab work package attended and key issues around collections as data, data-driven collections research, and the design of digital collection-based resources were discussed. Possible formats for the workshop and possible dates in 2023 were discussed.</p>	Attendance: Alistair Paterson (CTW), members of Sloane Lab.
08 Nov 2022	<p>The Sloane Lab data challenge: engaging with and aggregating our challenging pasts, Central London (UCL Bloomsbury campus)</p> <p>Focus group and workshop to explore innovative approaches and technological tools to manage, query, and visualize the data, including the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base and the Sloane Lab Data Atlas. Designed and produced by Alda Terracciano in collaboration with Marco Humbel, Foteini Valeonti, Daniele Metilli, Jawad Sadek, and Andreas Vlachidis as part of the MTSR Conference.</p>	<p>Target group: experts in data modelling, metadata, & semantics</p> <p>Number of participants: 19</p>
21 Feb 2023	<p>Who holds the data? Connecting cultivated plants to specimens in the Sloane Lab</p> <p>Consultation with representatives from the Heritage Seed Library to co-produce a workshop with members of community heritage organisations. Designed and produced by Alda Terracciano.</p>	<p>Target group: community heritage organisations</p> <p>Number of participants: 4</p>
26 Feb 2023	<p>Meeting with Australian Project Partner, Collecting the West (CTW).</p> <p>Meeting with the wider CTW team. It was confirmed that the Knowledge Exchange event will take place on 22-24 November 2023 in Melbourne, Australia and will be hosted by Deakin University. The selection of Sloane Lab team members to contribute to the event was made.</p>	Attendance: Wider CTW team (4 members), Sloane lab members Alicia Hughes, Jeremy Hill, Ciara Adeniyi-Jones

Conference Presentations, Talks and Interviews

Date	Descriptions	Attendance
13 Oct 2021	Co-I Nina Pearlman presented at a UCL Institute of Collections Webinar and introduced Sloane Lab internally.	Attendance: less than 50 with local and professional reach.
18 Nov 2021	Co-I Mark Carine co-organised a workshop with Queen Mary University: <i>Disciplinary and the early-modern herbarium</i> - A one-day research workshop. He referred to the Sloane Lab and underpinned the multidisciplinary nature of the project, an opportunity to engage researchers from different disciplines.	Attendance: less than 50 with local and professional reach.
03 Dec 2021	Julianne Nyhan Sloane Lab PI presented at Universität Bern seminar <i>Digitality/Digital Culture(s)</i> . Presentation topic: Loss, absence, and contestation in Digital Humanities through the lens of the collection of Hans Sloane (1660-1753)	Attendance: For PhD students and advanced Master students of the University of Bern. More than 50 with international and professional reach.
27 Jan 2022	Julianne Nyhan Chaired and presented at The Society for the History of Collections special meetings <i>New Perspectives on Sloane</i> to provide a platform for new research on Sloane.	Attendance: more than 50 with academics and students.
19 May 2022	Communicating Colonial Legacies Workshop A half day workshop organised by TaNC and hosted by Sloane Lab in UCL	7 Sloane Lab members were present at the Workshop. Total attendance 32, including delegates from other Discovery Projects and TaNC/AHRC.
5 – 10 Jun 2022	NHM PDRA Victoria Pickering presented at the Conference for the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections (SPNHC) Posters Session. Abstract title: <i>Mobilising data in the Natural History Museum's historical botanical collection</i>	Attendance: The estimated number of participants is 450 with international reach.

10 Jun 2022	<p>A deeper look at the Semantic Web, pt. 2 – The Sloane Lab</p> <p>Daniele Metilli presented the Sloane Lab in the context of the CLARIN workshop series "Digital Philology Meets Computational Linguistics", organised by the Venice Centre of Digital and Public Humanities at the University of Venice</p>	Attendance: less than 50 people of professional practitioners and students.
23 Jun 2022	<p>Nina Pearlman invited to panel discussion at the EdTechX summit in London. Panel discussion at the EdTechX summit in London that explores new trends at the intersection of education and Tech with respect to VR/AR and the metaverse.</p>	Attendance: less than 50 professional practitioners, policymakers, industry, and students with international reach.
01 Jul 2022	<p>Vicky Pickering presented a short talk at the Natural History Museum's monthly Collections and Culture Research theme meeting to introduce the Sloane Lab.</p>	Attendance: less than 50 Natural History Museum colleagues
05 – 08 Jul 2022	<p>Universeum 2022 (Belgium) – Poster section presentation of conference paper Interrogating collections' contested and challenging past through the SLOANE (GLAM) LAB (J. Nyhan, A. Vlachidis, A. Flinn, N. Pearlman, M. Humbel, D. Metilli, J. Sadek, F. Valeonti, M. Carine, V. Pickering & A. Terracciano).</p> <p>Research Fellows, Daniele Metilli and Marco Humbel are bursary awardees of the Universeum Pre-Conference Training Workshop (5-8 July). They co-presented the outcomes of the workshop.</p>	Attendance: about 100 with international reach from the University museums and archives sector.
15 Jul 2022	<p>Digital Humanities Summer School at Oxford - DHOxSS2022 (11 July 2022 – 15 July 2022). PI Julianne Nyhan presented keynote at Keble College Oxford. "Thinking through the place of absence in the grand challenges of the Digital Humanities and Humanities Data Science".</p>	Attendance: more than 50 with students and DH scholars.
08 – 10 Sep 2022	<p>The Digital Humanities Congress Sep 2022</p> <p>Deborah Leem, Andreas Vlachidis, Prof Julianne Nyhan (PI) - Presented paper 'Sir Han Slone's Information Architecture: From TEI to CSV for Data Analysis.'</p>	Attendance: approximately 60 professional practitioners, policymakers, and postgraduate students. National reach.

12 – 16 Sep 2022	<p>EUSN 2022 London, 6th European Conference on Social Networks</p> <p>The Sloane Lab team (Daniele Metilli; Andreas Vlachidis; Marco Humbel; Victoria Pickering; Mark Carine; Kim Sloan; Julianne Nyhan), presented paper 'Towards a network analysis of Hans Sloane's collection: A preliminary study' at 6th European Conference on Social Networks 12-16 September 2022 in University of Greenwich, London, UK.</p>	Attendance: approximately 85 professional practitioners and postgraduate students. International reach.
15 – 16 Sep 2022	<p>Bauhin Conference 2022 at University of Basel</p> <p>Co-I Dr Mark Carine presented at 'Documenting, understanding and opening the botanical collections of Hans Sloane (1660-1753)' at the conference. He also served as one of the Scientific Committee members for the conference.</p>	Attendance: Approximately 100 professional practitioners. International reach.
21 Oct 2022	<p>Interdisciplinary creative engagements with collections at UCL and beyond</p> <p>Nina Pearlman was a guest speaker presenting the Sloane Lab in the context of a session on public and private collections to undergraduate fine art students at the University of East London (UEL) BA Fine Art.</p>	Attendance: less than 10 local undergraduate students.
14 Nov 2022	<p>Der Schöne-Vortrag, titled 'Mind the Gap: Data absence, data silence, and data bias'</p> <p>PI Prof. Julianne Nyhan gave the Der Schöne-Vortrag, titled 'Mind the Gap: Data absence, data silence, and data bias' on 14th November 2022 at The Technical University of Berlin (TU Berlin)</p>	Attendance: approximately 100 professional practitioners, students, policymakers. International reach and engagement with the media as a channel to wider audiences.
07 Dec 2022	<p>Connecting Jamaican plants across Sloane collections</p> <p>Workshop to identify what expert users might want to do with data from various Sloane's datasets and explore the interoperability of the Sloane Lab database with external digital collections using a selection of specimen from Sloane's Voyage</p>	<p>Target group: Sloane's experts</p> <p>Number of participants: 10</p>

	to Jamaica. Designed by Alda Terracciano and produced in collaboration with Marco Humbel and Vicky Pickering.	
10 Jan 2023	<p>Bridging worlds: collaborative case studies in technology and art collections at UCL</p> <p>Nina Pearlman presented the Sloane Lab in the context of UCL case studies where collections meet technology at TRAN(S)MISSIONS how multimediality shapes interdisciplinary research in the field of Italian and Visual Culture Studies 3rd edition. Winter School.</p>	Attendance: approximately 25 people, primarily professional practitioners and students. International reach.
27 Mar 2023	<p>Challenges and Opportunities of Semantic Modelling and Enrichment in Small and Large Museum collections.</p> <p>Andreas Vlachidis presented at the International Seminar on <i>Semantic Web, Cultural Heritage, and Art Historical Knowledge: Conceptual Models, Ontologies, and Epistemological Implications</i>.</p>	Attendance: approximately 75 professional practitioners- academics and GLAM sector experts. International reach.
10 – 14 Jul 2023	<p>DH2023, Graz Austria</p> <p>The Sloane lab has accepted an invitation to partake in a panel presentation at the annual conference.</p>	Expected attendance: Professional practitioners associated with the international Digital Humanities (DH) community of scholars.

Research Approach

Our research approach is pursued across three principal strands – which are interconnected but discussed separately below for the purposes of clarity – technical elaboration and aggregation; participatory engagement; and collection case studies.

Technical Elaboration and Aggregation

This work of technical elaboration and aggregation can be conceptualised as a process of retro-engineering the envisaged public-facing, open-access Sloane Lab, which will contain the data, tools and services that can support the cross-collection search and the digitally-augmented exploration and reuse of digital cultural heritage collections. Working from the vision to the actual implementation, the following technical steps have been identified as essential to delivering the Lab:

1. Installation of computational infrastructure and architecture to support the lab.
2. Data identification, extraction, and enrichment.
3. Iterative elaboration of a unified schema and mapping of Sloane's structured and unstructured data to this schema.
4. Ongoing ingestion of data into the Knowledge Graph (triple store).
5. Development of query and visualisation dashboard, including tools and services that allow that data to be Findable, Cross-searchable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
6. Iterative User-testing of interfaces and approaches.
7. Publishing and deployment.

See Annex for Figure 2. Mathematical Instruments 54.

Some of the most significant challenges in the development of the Sloane Lab data model and knowledge base are the handling of uncertainty, the multivocality of the collection (e.g., conflicting data from different records about the same object), data absences (i.e., gaps in the records), the difficulty of classifying objects, and the fact that some of the objects described in the historical catalogues are now lost. Another important challenge is the handling of the complex stratification of multiple identifiers that have been assigned to the objects over the centuries. With regard to this, one of our goals is to provide a unique and persistent identifier to each entity that is described in the knowledge base, relying on existing institutional IDs when possible.

In parallel with the development of the data model, we are also working on the integration of vocabularies and typologies, either provided by the partner institutions or imported from external sources. One significant issue that we need to solve is that institution-owned vocabularies are often represented in proprietary formats and not made freely available to the public. Publishing some of these vocabularies available as Linked Data (in particular through the use of SKOS) would help us reach the goals of the project, and further the TaNC goal of integrating data from multiple institutions. Discussions with the partner institutions about how best to integrate their vocabularies into the Sloane Lab knowledge base are ongoing.

Finally, another important issue that we are facing in the data aggregation is the management of the copyright of the datasets. While the historical data is in the public domain, the contemporary data is owned by the partner institutions, which have different approaches, perspectives and needs with regard to copyright. When aggregating the data into a single knowledge base, it is necessary to strike a balance between the requirements set by the different institutions, striving to publish as open data whenever possible, but also supporting multiple licensing regimes when publishing the data.

Participatory Engagement

This project does not view the computational research of collections as separate from public engagement and impact. Accordingly, this strand of the project asks questions of the interface between collections as data, co-design and public engagement: how can we involve members of the public, researchers, curators and heritage organisations in the machine-actionable contextualisation of individual objects and collections, enabling community-sourced knowledge to enhance and even challenge existing Western-derived descriptions and conceptions? In answering such questions, we aim to unify historical and present-day collections and records across taxonomy, geography, context, and audience in a way that accommodates the interests of publics, expert communities, and information organisations.

To pave the way to get to know and build the Sloane Lab community, we have introduced an online questionnaire to identify barriers and challenges in accessing and using dispersed collections. We have also opened an online form to capture expressions of interest to advance co-design activities, which has thus far recorded circa 100 responses that discuss the use of collections data and individuals' interest in participating in future Sloane Lab activities. In recent months, considerable effort has been given to elaborating a robust plan for the planned second cycle of participatory engagement activities, which will include up to 10 workshops, in addition to one-to-one sessions, testing session, use cases focus groups, and demo sessions with individuals and communities. The activities planned will be linked to the technical team's Sloane Lab Query Service and Knowledge Base tasks; the Sloane Lab data model; the Sloane Lab Data Atlas; and the Sloane Lab API and web application.

The flagship of the participatory strand comprises of 10 Community Fellows appointed through an open call. Fellows will be given the funds and technical assistance they require to undertake a creative, research led or practice-based project on the digital national collection using the Sloane Lab.

In development is a communications strategy as well as a glossary that will inform and support all aspects of the Sloane Lab engagement including exhibition outputs as well as research and engagement outputs produced by Sloane Lab Community Fellows.

Collections Team

Work at the Natural History Museum (NHM) focusses on data mobilisation of Hans Sloane's botanical collections, the largest surviving component of Sloane's collections (see Annex for NHM Data Mobilisation). In parallel with this work, the NHM team has worked with the Museum's Data Management Team to develop specifications for enhancements to the Collections Management System so that data relating to specimens

mounted on folios that are contained in bound volumes and curated under pre-Linnean polynomial names can be better represented in the CMS and, by extension, the outward-facing data portal.

Two other pieces of Sloane lab work are also ongoing at the NHM. The first is provision of inventory level records for all specimens in the herbarium. The anticipated completion for this curatorial task is November 2024. This work will provide the framework within the NHM CMS within which the plant names extracted from Ray's *Historia Plantarum* will be integrated and then made available via the NHM portal both to the public and the Sloane Lab knowledgebase. The integration of these two datasets (specimens and names) into Sloane Lab will allow a better understanding of those parts of the herbarium that were annotated and named and those parts that were not. It will thus allow questions to be asked regarding how Sloane managed his entire herbarium collection and how he valued it.

In parallel with this, an AHRC-funded student working on the contexts in which specimens in the Sloane Herbarium were collected, is delivering an enriched and marked up version of J.S. Dandy's (1958) *The Sloane Herbarium* (see Annex for J.S. Dandy's Sloane Herbarium).

In addition to work on data mobilisation, the NHM has also been contributing to the work of the participatory team on the design of a third workshop focussed on cultivated plants and Sloane's collection of vegetables and vegetable substances that will take place in April 2023. The NHM is also contributing to work on the touring exhibition for which the NHM is likely to be the largest contributor of objects.

Attention is now also turning to the planning of a collaborative case study on the Sloane collections' representation and acknowledgement of its colonial context, to be undertaken collaboratively by NHM, BM and UCL. Expanding the scope to work on collections held across institutions and on those catalogues not previously addressed by Enlightenment Architectures, the purpose of this trans-institutional case study is two-fold: it will act as an incubator and proving ground for the technologies and processes developed by this project, applying and evaluating them across the breadth of Sloane's catalogues and collection data, leading to further refinements of the project's automated and semi-automated workflows and techniques. It will also advance empirical and critical critiques of data-driven and quantitative approaches to identifying and visualising the colonial processes, infrastructures, agents, and provenance of the national collection as embodied in Sloane's collection. Utilising the semantic modelling of entities that this project will unlock, we will, for the first time, be able to reassemble and map the stated geographical provenance of objects and specimens across the entirety of Sloane's collection; the role of trading companies and enterprises in the shipping of objects and individuals connected with the collection, creating new knowledge about Sloane's collections as a product of colonial activities. The case study will directly inform the planned physical and touring exhibition and has the potential to significantly impact understanding of the research capacity that can be created by making collections machine-readable and computable with open technologies.

A touring exhibition will form part of the established National Programme of the British Museum touring exhibitions. These are designed to best support the partner museum's ambitions and audiences. Those museums will shape the focus and nature of this proposed Sloane-focused exhibition. The exhibition will travel to at least four venues across the UK, including our project partners in Down County Museum.

One of the promised outputs of the Sloane Lab project is a Knowledge Exchange workshop with the project's only international partner, Collecting the West (University of Western Australia). Initial exploratory consultation between the BM and the Collecting the West team was held during a visit from Alistair Paterson from University of Western Australia at the BM on 2 November 2022. Members of each Sloane Lab work package attended and key issues around collections as data, data-driven collections research and the design of digital collection-based resources were discussed. Possible formats and dates for the workshop in 2023 were discussed. A second consultation was held via Teams on 26 February 2023 with the wider Collecting the West team. It was confirmed that the Knowledge Exchange event will take place on 22-24 November 2023 in Melbourne, Australia and will be hosted by Deakin University.

Research Results

The main outcome of the project will be a digital platform that can support research on digital national collections. This platform, the Sloane Lab, will comprise: a search interface (to the reunified present-day collections, historical catalogues and external resources), content (Sloane's historical catalogues as machine actionable datasets for reuse), tools for managing and researching the data (to support, e.g. network analysis, text analysis or AI-led interrogation of collections and records); documentation covering uses of the data (e.g. schemas, licensing details); and an engagement demonstrator that facilitates the participation of heritage institutions in the Sloane Lab (e.g. white paper and code-books).

An important research outcome of the project will be the methodologies and instruments that the project will devise not only for the technical aspects of pursuing collections as data research but also for working with diverse communities. Accordingly, the project will closely document not only its research outcomes that pertain to the new kinds of questions that individuals and communities might wish to ask of Sloane's collections, including the language they want to use; it will also document and make freely available the methodologies it is pursuing to support this work, including instruments for working with diverse communities, like interview questionnaires, workshop activities and so on.

The foundations upon which the seven technical steps listed in the Research Methods section must be built are now well advanced in the following areas:

Data Mobilisation

This concerns all those tasks that are responsible for producing machine actionable data from previously unstructured textual resources, their modelling and alignment to the Sloane Lab data model and their enrichment with semantic definitions and potential linking to Linked Data. The NHMs Ray's *Plantarum* has been identified and prioritised as a dataset for mobilisation due to its uniqueness and key role in reconnecting currently dispersed botanical information. Sloane's personal copy of the *Plantarum* is unique in the sense that it holds access to Sloane herbarium specimens by connecting polynomial plant names to volumes and pages of the herbarium. The resource contains an extremely rich and complex set of data that combine printed material (i.e., plant names) and hand-written marginalia (i.e., volume and page references to the herbarium). Overall, the mobilization task addressed approximately 2,000 pages originating from two volumes, containing approximately 7,500 plant names, 4,200 marginalia referencing 17,000 specimens in the herbarium, and 1,300 header and footer segments containing an additional set of 3,500 handwritten plant names.

Various workflows are being implemented to mobilising the data types contained in the two volumes of the *Plantarum*. The printed text of polynomial plant names has been OCRed and post processed. Word level and character level error rates have been calculated to inform the post-processing phase which involves automatic spellchecking based on specialised domain vocabulary. Plant name entries couple both preferred (authority) versions and synonyms and a further processing and semantic enrichment is currently conducted for producing finer structures of plant name entries. In addition to the automatic

OCR driven method, the data mobilisation task involves manual transcription of marginalia. Human involvement is critical to this task due to limited capacity of automated methods to rectify erroneously detected numbers. Further manual transcription tasks have also been specified that concern transcription of header and footer segments from the *Plantarum*. Such segments contain hand-written polynomial plant names that complement the list of printed plant names and likewise marginalia they also contain references to herbarium volume and pages of specimens. The complexity of such hand-written segments in terms of layout and reference numbers do-not lend to automated methods.

The potential of HTR models for automatic transcription of additional manuscript catalogues is being tested by comparing generic Transkribus HTR models and AWS Textract. Sloane's catalogue of Miscellanies served as a testbed as its characteristics (i.e., layout, script, and annotations) are representative for the whole collection of catalogues. The test results were compared with the outcomes of an earlier bespoke HTR model for Sloane's hand, developed by Marco Humbel for his Master dissertation.¹ The evaluation assessed the need to train a bespoke HTR model for Sloane's hand by combining latest public Transkribus models with enhanced training data for Sloane's hand.

Data Aggregation and Knowledge Base Development

The data aggregation and knowledge base development has moved to the "extended alpha" stage, meaning that we have expanded beyond historical catalogues towards the aggregation of contemporary datasets provided by partner institutions, starting from the Natural History Museum (NHM) and then moving on to the British Museum (BM) data. To date, 10 datasets have been ingested from NHM, and three from the historical catalogues that were annotated by the Enlightenment Architectures project. In total, the knowledge base currently contains more than 145,000 statements about more than 14,000 records represented as information objects, describing the same number of physical objects. We are now working to ingest the full dataset of about 15,000 Sloane-related records from BM, thereby more than doubling the size of the knowledge base. More data will later be ingested from additional historical catalogues and from datasets provided by the British Library (BL).

The integration of contemporary data requires significant changes to the Sloane Lab data model discussed in the previous report, which has been extended to represent domain-specific data. For example, the NHM data requires the representation of species, including binomial species names and historical polynomial names. The BM data requires the representation of data related to human-made objects such as materials, techniques, production dates, etc. The integration of contemporary data from multiple sources has surfaced new challenges and a review of our initial approach centred on information objects, which is currently ongoing with the help of the partner institutions.

Data Environment and Dissemination

Data Environment

Sloane Lab's Data Atlas, which is a visual representation of the Sloane Collections, has evolved into a robust process for visualising and ultimately understanding complex data environments that feature datasets dispersed across different information systems and infrastructures. In its most complete version to date, the map metaphor for the Data Atlas has now been consolidated. As such, the Data Atlas is comprised of *continents*, which indicate institutions hosting either physical artefacts, or digital surrogates of the Sloane Collections. This approach has allowed us to navigate Sloane Lab's data environment more seamlessly, facilitating better decision-making during the course of the project. A weakness of this approach is that it does not prevent duplication. In order to address that issue, duplication is managed with footnotes that serve as shortcuts between replicated resources (e.g., *Fossils vol. 1*, which belongs to the Natural History Museum, but can also be found in the continent of the Enlightenment Architectures).

Beyond location, physical or virtual, which is visualised with continents, the Data Atlas has been developed to also depict the state of mapped datasets. Depending on the type of the resource, i.e., historical manuscript, or contemporary database, different categories apply to indicate the level of digitisation. Such digitisation levels vary from imaged and scanned resources, to transcribed and OCR'd, to fully structured TEI digitised, whereas contemporary datasets hold register of records (catalogued) and images (imaged objects). Within each continent, different columns linked with arrows indicate the level of digitisation of each tangible resource, be it a manuscript, or a collection of artefacts. Colour coding indicates the level of accessibility for all mapped resources (ranging from tangible artefacts that can only be accessed at the host institution, to fully-digitised, publicly available resources). Beyond continuous improvements to the accurate cataloguing and representation of all resources, recent changes to the Data Atlas have included the addition of the Adam Matthew database, which includes 94 books that were collected by Sloane, which have also been fully digitised and are available in a machine-readable format. Finally, the Data Atlas demonstrates at a glance where and in what format all of Sloane's Historic Manuscripts are today.

Dissemination and Documentation

The web presence of the project has also been strengthened. The project's central hub, sloanelab.org is an up-to-date resource, featuring all the project's dissemination and public engagement activities. All of the project's participatory workshops and events are organised within the top-level menu item "Participatory Co-Design & Research", whereas material from the technical team and other activities are organised by format and author(s) (accessible through the "Sloane Lab Framework"). All activity can be browsed through "News & Updates", which is an up-to-date feed of all the project's public-facing activities. Beyond the website, the project enjoys the following spaces which are constantly updated and maintained, i.e. GitHub, which hosts all datasets and work that can be publicly shared by the Technical Team as of now, and the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base, which is still under development. Finally, the dissemination of Linked Data is being investigated, with Metaphactory (the platform powering Sloane Lab's Knowledge Base) emerging as a potential route, as it supports the publishing of Linked Data, providing also a SPARQL end point, as well as web pages for accessing all published data.

Participatory

Since the last report, a number of participatory events have been designed and delivered.

Planned participatory activities began in October 2022 with a half day digital jam workshop held at the Natural History Museum that attracted 20 participants as part of the NHM Explorers Family Festival, with a particular focus on African Caribbean family history researchers. Entitled *Searching for Jamaican plants in the Sloane Lab*, this workshop's aim was to understand use of plain English vs/specialised terminology for botanical specimens from Sloane's Voyage to Jamaica, their cultural meaning and uses of online catalogues. The target group was British-Caribbean people interested in plants. The workshop succeeded in acquiring knowledge on ways in which non-specialist users engage with Sloane's botanical Jamaican collection. The workshop gathered information that can be used to develop a search facility to better accommodate non-academic users and remove barriers created by specialist language in the catalogues; raised awareness of Sloane's collections amongst British-Caribbean people; and produced new knowledge that can be added to the NHM online public repository.

On 8 November 2022, the participatory team also designed and produced a focus group and workshop held at UCL for a range of people with expertise in data modelling, metadata and semantics. Organised as part of the 16th International Conference on Metadata and Semantics Research

conference and in collaboration with members of the technical team, this successful event involved 19 participants. This workshop entitled *The Sloane Lab data challenge: engaging with & aggregating our challenging pasts* explored innovative approaches and technological tools to manage, query, and visualize the data, including the Sloane Lab Knowledge Base and the Sloane Lab Data Atlas.

On 7 December 2022, another participatory workshop was held at UCL with 10 participants, entitled *Connecting Jamaican plants across Sloane collections*. This workshop was used to identify what expert users might want to do with data from various Sloane's datasets and to explore the interoperability of the Sloane Lab database with external digital collections using a selection of specimen from Sloane's Voyage to Jamaica. This workshop was a collaboration with the NHM Collections team and targeted those with varying expertise in Botanical specimens and interest in Sloane's collections.

The team has also held a consultation with representatives from the Heritage Seed Library to co-produce a workshop with members of community heritage organisations which is expected to be held in April 2023. The aim is to understand the relevance of historical catalogues in contemporary society through represented plants cultivated in the 17th and 18th centuries, and the interoperability of Sloane Lab with external online repositories.

The significant amount of data that has been collected through the participatory events held so far is currently being reviewed and methods that can support a rich engagement with and analysis of this data are being studied so that an effective workflow for the analysis of this data can be established.

As we particularly welcome applications to the Community Fellows calls from people of the Global Majority and other groups who are underrepresented in and by the Heritage and Academic sectors, the legislative aspects of the calls have been addressed. Research was undertaken to identify dissemination channels that could ensure the call would reach a wide audience. 25 were used (e.g.: Caribbean Studies Group, Alan Turing Institute, Young Historian Project, Global DH mailing list). The first call was

announced in November 2022, 19 applications were received (from individuals based in the UK, Uganda, Italy, India, Israel, Greece, Sri Lanka) with proposed topics including History & Horticulture, Collections & Enslavement, Museum Taxonomies and Critical Museum Studies. Interviews were held in February 2023 and three fellowships have been offered for the period 27 March – 23 June 2023, meeting Sloane Lab global majority recruitment objectives. Shortlisting for the second round is expected to commence in May 2023 with recruitment for round three to follow later in the year, for completion in 2024.

The Sloane Lab seeks to ensure the transferability of its findings to heritage institutions beyond the national institutions.

Following a wide-ranging literature review and the drawing up of the relevant instruments, a series of 11 interviews were conducted with representatives from heritage institutions. Interviews with 10 organisations with 18 individuals were conducted to understand aspirations, needs and constraints regarding virtually unified collections. These interviews have been transcribed and approved, and data-analysis and write-up is in progress. The findings of this aspect of the project are expected to have the potential to inform the longer-term development of collections as a data strategy in the UK and provide clear guidance to TaNC about areas of investment that might be prioritised to support heritage organisations' engagement with the digitisation of collections over the longer term.

Since August 2022, work on the Sloane Lab Touring Exhibition has significantly progressed. It has the provisional title 'For the Curious and the Interested' (this title draws on Sloane's original intended audience for this collection when it came to the BM in 1753). The exhibition concept has been developed to encourage museum partners to explore themes around global collecting practices in the 17th and 18th centuries. The physical exhibition will ultimately aim to demonstrate the types of stories and connections that it will be possible to make via the Sloane Lab digital portal (*see Annex for BM Touring Exhibition*).

Project Outputs

- A digital platform, the Sloane Lab, which can support a new kind of data-driven engagement with the national collection.
- At least six co-authored articles will be published in international, peer-reviewed scholarly journals like the International Journal of Heritage Studies and Journal of Documentation in order to present the outcomes of the project to the international academic community.
- A series of outputs that document, and where possible, make executable, key aspects of the project's technical and methodological elaboration. Output in the final stages of the project, they will be output in a way that is appropriate to the eventual form each respective output takes, for example, policy-based recommendations in a white paper; best practice reports on, e.g. approaches to automating semantic and structural annotation of digital cultural heritage as a narrative report or dataset, whether released as a Jupyter notebook, via GitHub or another publicly assessable data repository.
- A Touring Exhibition for partner museums will be developed around a prominent object or objects in Sloane's collection chosen to best convey the work of the project and the stories about these objects that can only be told because of bringing the collection together.
- Changes to permanent exhibitions in the British Museum Enlightenment Gallery are also foreseen.
- Victoria Pickering; Charles Jarvis; Mark Carine (2023). Hans Sloane's Collection of Vegetables and Vegetable Substances [Data set]. Natural History Museum. <https://doi.org/10.5519/lp5a5t1d>

Early Outputs:

- PI J. Nyhan interviewed in: Jack, Andrew.
- 2021. 'Search for a Digital National Collection'. Financial Times, 22 November 2021. <https://www.ft.com/content/1282bb6e-bbde-4449-8efc-42b43335f8f1>
- Sloan K, (2022). Sloane's Antiquities. Providing a 'Body of History' Through Beads, Bottles, Brasses and Busts. Collective Wisdom - Collecting in the Early Modern Academy. (pp. 211-234). <https://doi.org/10.1484/M.TECHNE-EB.5.119385>
- Sloane Lab Newsletter - published six issues so far:
The Sloane Lab Newsletters introduce the project team members and provide updates about the project to the key stakeholders and interested individuals. As of January 2023, it has 112 subscribers and an international reach (Australia, USA and Canada).
 - Issue 1: 22nd November 2021
 - Issue 2: 8th February 2022
 - Issue 3: 11th April 2022
 - Issue 4: 21st June 2022
 - Issue 5: 17th October 2022
 - Issue 6: 7th December 2022

Cross Project Collaboration

Collaboration with other TaNC projects to date has centred around the technical aspects of the project, specifically on ontologies and vocabularies for data modelling. We have benefited from knowledge exchange with the Unpath'd Waters project, who shared their Towards the UNPATH'D Waters Ontology draft report with us, which sets out "a core ontology to which UNPATH data providers will map their individual database schema, thereby ensuring interoperability between diverse resources" (UNPATH'D Waters 2021).

Sustainability and Infrastructure

Project management data, like progress reports, communication, schedule, notes, ethics and governance documentation, are being stored in UCL's Microsoft SharePoint and OneDrive for business server, managed by UCL Information Services Division (ISD) and backed-up daily. Our Sloane Lab SharePoint interface is available to all Sloane Lab team members based in UCL, the Natural History Museum and the British Museum.

Due to slow response rates, institutionally imposed security barriers to public facing URLs and scalability of resources, we have decided to move the project's infrastructure to AWS cloud services. Our current cloud services utilise Lightsail, EC2, Textract, Lambda, Route 53, Cognito, Backup, VPC, Certificate Manager, IAM, Event bridge. Two separate servers have been deployed. The WordPress server that hosts the project's website carries a specification of 512 MB RAM- 1 vCPU, 20 GB SSD. The development server that hosts the knowledge base carries the specification 2 GB RAM - 8vCPU - 200 GiB SSD - Operating System: Ubuntu 22.

Long-term data storage will be supported by UCL's Research Data Storage. The UCL Research Data service guarantees the preservation of research data for 10 years or more. The back-up is daily, and the service can be used during the lifetime of the project and after. The triple store data of the Knowledge Base will be stored in these services, together with any additional research data. In addition, the technology stack of the VM and server configuration will be stored as a ready deployable Docker image.

It is also hoped that long-term storage will be supported by the BM and NHM, via their collections management systems, which guarantee preservation without time limit.

Interim Recommendations

We are now approaching the half-way point of this project and while we have already carried out a significant number of activities, and made progress across all of our collections, technical and participatory work packages, we have not as of yet fully analysed our emerging data with the rigor that is required to make recommendations with confidence. For this reason, at this time we can only make the following recommendation:

Irrespective of the usefulness of the digital tools and processes that will be developed by the Towards a National Collection projects, Heritage institutions will almost certainly feel it necessary to license their data and metadata under a range of licenses, and not only CC Zero. Accordingly, it will be essential for any national collection to be able to accommodate this at the aggregate level of its infrastructure, and not to expect that it can attain uniformity of licensing across the heritage sector.

Contacts

Nyhan, Julianne - j.nyhan@ucl.ac.uk

Flinn, Andrew - a.flinn@ucl.ac.uk

Pearlman, Nina - n.pearlman@ucl.ac.uk

Vlachidis, Andreas - a.vlachidis@ucl.ac.uk

Jeremy Hill - JHill@britishmuseum.org

Mark Carine - m.carine@nhm.ac.uk

Annex

Annex1: Technical Architecture

Figure 1: Sloane Lab Architecture

Source: Dr Andreas Vlachidis, UCL

Annex 2: Knowledge Base Depiction

Figure 2: Mathematical Instruments 54

Source: Dr Andreas Vlachidis, UCL

Annex 3: NHM Data Mobilisation

At the NHM at present, there are catalogue records available for only c. 2,500 specimens out of c. 138,000 specimens that the collection contains (2%). Through the use of innovative Digital Humanities approaches to mobilise and enrich the data contained in the six volumes that Sloane used to catalogue his botanical collections, enhancements to the NHM Collections Management System (CMS) and associated curatorial and research work, all specimens in Sloane's botanical will be digitally represented in the Sloane Lab through this project. For Sloane's collection of vegetables and vegetable substances, a transcription of the three-volume catalogue containing 12,732 entries, linked to surviving objects in the collection, is being made publicly available through the Natural History Museum's data portal (<https://data.nhm.ac.uk/dataset/sloane-vegetable-substances>) from where they may also be ingested into the Sloane Lab knowledgebase. This work has now been completed. In parallel with this, specimen records are being enriched with images where these are available and the NHM Data Management Team have made available an easy-to-use app that can be used by NHM associates to add any images they hold to records.

For Sloane's herbarium of c.138,000 surviving specimens, the NHM team has been working with the technical team on protocols to capture the annotations in John Ray's *Historia Plantarum* that were used by Sloane to encode the physical location of specimens within the 335 *Horti Sicci* that his herbarium contains. Protocols for capturing marginalia have now been developed and work to capture those and link them to the names used by Ray is now underway. Header and footer annotations will be captured using double-key transcription for which the NHM team is helping to develop the specification.

J.S. Dandy's Sloane Herbarium

J.S. Dandy's (1958) *The Sloane Herbarium* provides a broad overview of the contents of each of the 335 *Horti Sicci* together with information on the collectors and collecting localities for specimens where those data were recorded. The data on collectors and localities from this doctoral research project will also be integrated into the herbarium specimen dataset and made available through the data portal. Thus, through Sloane Lab work on Ray's *Historia Plantarum*, curatorial work on CMS inventory records and doctoral research involving the extraction of data from Dandy (1958), a rich dataset with information, where available, on the names Sloane used to catalogue specimens, together with details of the people who contributed those plants and where they were collected from, will be made available at the scale of the entire herbarium. This work will be completed in the first quarter of 2024.

Data enrichment, to ensure that *Sloane's botanical collection online* can not only be made cross-searchable but fully integrated with the Sloane Lab. Working presently on three volumes of Ray's *Historia Plantarum*, in close collaboration with the technical team, the data this contains is now being enriched and linked to records of specimens held in the Natural History Museum's content management system (CMS) and images of those specimens where they are available. Following this, work will focus on the three volumes of Sloane's *Vegetable Substances* (VS) catalogue, editing/cleaning of VS catalogue data (three volumes, 12,700+ entries), linking people and places in catalogue data to unique identifiers from the CMS and establishing protocol for serving digital images of catalogues from NHM and implement for VS catalogues.

In parallel with the Sloane Lab project, a doctoral research student, funded by the AHRC London Arts and Humanities Partnership programme is working on the contexts in which specimens in the Sloane Herbarium were collected. This project will deliver an enriched and marked up version of J.S. Dandy's (1958) *The Sloane Herbarium*. This work provides a broad overview of the contents of each of the 335 *Horti Sicci* together with information on the collectors and collecting localities for specimens where those data were recorded. The data on collectors and localities from this doctoral research project will also be integrated into the herbarium specimen dataset and made available through the data portal. Thus, through Sloane Lab work on Ray's *Historia Plantarum*, curatorial work on CMS inventory records and doctoral research involving the extraction of data from Dandy (1958), a rich dataset with information, where available, on the names Sloane used to catalogue specimens, together with details of the people who contributed those plants and where they were collected from, will be made available at the scale of the entire herbarium.

Annex 4: British Museum Touring Exhibition

For the touring exhibition it is important to translate the wider objectives of the Sloane Lab project into achievable objectives for a physical exhibition. These objectives are:

- To reconnect objects from the historical collection of Sir Hans Sloane
- To explore contemporary understandings of historical objects
- To address this and similar collections links with slavery and colonialism
- To encourage a co-curation approach to the development of exhibition content and programming
- To showcase the relevant collections of partner institutions
- To develop and build relationships with underrepresented communities.

Down County Museum, Downpatrick, Northern Ireland	20 January – 13 April 2024
Amgueddfa Ceredigion Museum, Aberystwyth, Wales	27 April – 20 July 2024
David Livingstone Birth Place, Blantyr, Scotland	3 August – 26 October 2024

The Sloane Lab Exhibition Programme Manager was appointed, and Rosalyn Tyler began the role on 7 November 2022. From the exhibition concept, a Call for Partners was developed to openly advertise and promote the 2024 exhibition opportunity. This call was released on 6 January 2023 and circulated and promoted widely among British Museum and local and individual networks. Eight expressions of interest were received from all over the UK. The Sloane Lab Project Curator and Exhibition Manager and the BM Collections Care registrar subsequently selected two partner venues (in addition to the Lead partner, Down County Museum in Northern Ireland) based on how interested museums' goals aligned with the exhibition objectives and practical requirements, such as suitable space and GIS standards. The final selection includes a museum in each of the devolved countries in the UK.

Progress has been made on other tasks including: developing a brief for the tender for a 2D exhibition designer (due to be appointed by 21 April 2023) who will create an overall look and feel and then work with the venues and their partners to shape the exhibition design in the lead up to their respective openings; developing a plan for supporting project documentation of participatory methodology, including participatory principles, a co-creation framework, participant remuneration guidance, a glossary of museum terminology and an MOU template.

Preliminary work has begun on collaboratively designing an evaluation plan with the partner venues with objectives, outcomes and outputs agreed upon collectively. A budget has been forecast for the tour allocating funding to the design, transportation, freelance role, and evaluation as well as the estimated expenditure on travel for British Museum staff to partner venues for support of the project development, and the remuneration of participants in line with the benchmarked fee. As a result, it is estimated each venue will engage with 8-10 participants on average twice a month for three hours for the duration of the project.

Initial discussions have begun with BM Press to plan a public announcement for the exhibition and a strategy to communicate with other stakeholders including TaNC Comms, NHM and BL. Consultation with registrars at NHM and BL about logistical and legal requirements for loaning objects has resulted in the agreement that BM will act as primary co-ordinator but each partner will contract directly with NHM and BL for the loans of objects. The BM Collections Care Registrar Alice Christen will act as the primary loan coordinator, acting as an intermediary/agent between the borrowing exhibition venues and the National lenders. Transport agents have been asked for quotes for the tour, with a deadline of 29 March 2023.

Significant progress on consultation with staff at the lead exhibition venue, Down County Museum in Northern Ireland and other stakeholders at the Sir Hans Sloane Center in Killyleagh has been made since August 2022. Following interest from DCM, the Project Curator and Exhibition Manager proposed and explored a collaboration with Sloane Lab Participatory Team to integrate participatory activity in NI into exhibition planning process. We have designed and will deliver a two-part activity with DCM and their partners in NI around the exhibition and the co-design of the Sloane Lab portal on 9 May and 20 June.